

Q33 - If you worked during your paternity leave, what were the reasons that led you to work during this period?

LABEL	#	Father's Answer
Research and teaching demands	12	As a researcher, my duties kept the same (reviewing papers, conducting research, supervising students, etc.)
		Mostly quick communication with students
		Precisei corrigir algumas provas que estavam pendentes.
		Resolver o problema do acúmulo de atividade que geralmente um professor possui.
		Orientação de alunos, escrita de artigos, coordenação de projetos, que são atividades que não param
		Os estudantes não podiam ficar sem aulas e não tinha um substituto formal.
		I was in a class. It's needed to finish
		Atividade de pesquisa
		Projects and deadlines
		Respostas de e-mails, projetos de pesquisa, orientações.
		Não pude deixar de atender demandas relacionadas à pesquisa e ao ensino.
		Atividades de orientação remotas.
Lack of a person to replace me	9	Dependência da empresa com a minha pessoa
		I was the computer science course coordinator at the time and the institution has no deputy coordinator.
		Problems in a client that only I could quickly resolve.
		Just need to have a few customers meetings that needed me and answered some questions from the team that only I had the answers
		Support unanswered team questions
		Some tasks were performed only by me.
		Transformation project and lack os skills to replace me.
		Durante a paternidade exercí trabalho formal fora da minha área de atuação e informal dentro da minha área para que conseguir manter a família. Durante o mesmo período, ainda realizava o curso universitário em faculdade pública federal.
		Falta de substituto, tarefas de grande complexidade, grande acúmulo de serviço.
		A legislação brasileira, e o tempo para cumprir o doutorado.
		Prazo de entrega de funcionalidades

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Deadlines	6	Entrega de projetos
		The deadlines were set before the paternity leave and were not changed
		Deadlines
		Deadlines.
Legal issues	4	A legislação brasileira, e o tempo para cumprir o doutorado.
		There was no law for paternity leave
		Em 2009 quando minha filha nasceu legalmente só havia 5 dias corridos para quem era CLT.
		Paternity leave is exclusive to women.
Financial issues	4	A falta de preparação financeira adequada para a situação.
		Minha esposa estava com contrato de trabalho suspenso e não recebeu nada de licença maternidade
		Money
		I was a freelancer at one of the jobs, they had bills to pay and I couldn't help but make money
Previous commitments	4	complete some commitments
		Correção de bugs.
		Ongoing projects, part-time leave.
		Day to day meetings
Unemployed when the child was born	3	have not worked
		Não trabalhei.
		I wasn't employed. But I was still studying to graduate.
Performed only urgent work	3	Responder email, basicamente
		orientação de aluno (só os mais importantes para mim) de maneira beeeeeeeem breve
		Some urgent research work
Work do not stop	2	I was in a project that I played a fundamental role and I did not need to be way since my last daughter born at Friday evening
		I was software house coordinator / engineering and projects did not stopped as team and customers solicitations

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Company demands	2	<p>Although I was at paternity leave, it was the end of the academic semester and I had to evaluate some final exams and do some course bureaucracy ("close" content, frequency and grades diaries). I also had to some minor coordinator tasks (only one to two hours or work, but, still, work).</p> <p>Company demand</p>
No paternity leave	1	At the time there was no paternity leave and it made no difference to me either.
I did not work during the paternity leave	1	nao
No need of paternity leaving	1	The needs during my daughter's growth could be met even while working.